

Oxidation of allyl alcohol by periodate in aqueous alkaline medium

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Manuscript received 29 July 1998, revised 4 December 1998, accepted 5 January 1999

The periodate oxidation of allyl alcohol in aqueous alkaline medium has a 1 : 1 stoichiometry and exhibits unit order in $[\text{IO}_4^-]$ and less than unit order each in [allyl alcohol] and [alkali]. The reaction proceeds via the formation of an oxidant-substrate complex and its subsequent decomposition to yield a free radical and an intermediate, $\text{I}(\text{vi})$, followed by the other fast step to give the products. $\text{H}_2\text{IO}_6^{3-}$ is found to be the active species of periodate.

The activity of periodic acid as an oxidising agent varies greatly as a function of pH and is capable of subtle control. In acid solution, it is one of the most powerful oxidising agents known, quantitatively and rapidly converting manganese(II) salts to permanganate, while in alkaline solution, it is slightly less oxidising than hypochlorite. In alkaline medium, periodate exists as different species involving multiple equilibria¹ and it needs to know the active form of oxidant in the reaction. However, there are numerous reports² on oxidation of organic compounds.

Kinetic studies on the oxidation of allyl alcohol with different oxidants such as potassium permanganate, chromic acid, vanadium(V), manganese pyrophosphate, chloramine-T and silver have been reported³. In the present study, the oxidation of allyl alcohol by periodate in aqueous alkaline medium is presented in order to understand the active species of periodate in such medium.

Results and Discussion

Stoichiometry : Different sets of reaction mixtures containing different concentrations of periodate and allyl alcohol were allowed to react for 24 h at 25°. When periodate concentration was higher than that of allyl alcohol the total oxidant concentration was found by iodometry⁴, and after accounting for the remaining oxidant concentration, the concentration of iodate formed was derived. Under the condition, $[\text{AA}] > [\text{IO}_4^-]$, when the periodate had fully reacted, the unreacted allyl alcohol was estimated⁵ by addition of an excess of chloramine-T followed by iodometric titration. Acrolein was found to be the main product as evidenced by spot test⁶. Test for acrylic acid⁷ was negative. Another product, iodate was determined iodometrically. The results were in agreement with a 1 : 1 stoichiometry,

Reaction order : The kinetic runs of oxidation of allyl alcohol by periodate in alkaline medium were followed at

different initial concentrations of oxidant, substrate and alkali in turn keeping all other concentrations constant. The orders were obtained from log-log plots of initial rates versus concentrations. The initial rates, obtained by the plane mirror method⁸, were reproducible within $\pm 4\%$. The periodate concentration was varied from 1.0×10^{-3} to 1.0×10^{-2} mol dm⁻³ at constant concentration of allyl alcohol, alkali and perchlorate (Table 1). The order in [periodate] was found to be unity. From the plot of log (initial rate) versus log [AA], the order of reaction in allyl alcohol was found to be less than unity in the concentration range 2.0×10^{-2} to 2.0×10^{-1} mol dm⁻³.

Table 1. Effect of [Allyl alcohol], [Periodate] and [Alkali] on the periodate oxidation of allyl alcohol in aqueous alkaline medium*

$10^2[\text{AA}]$ mol dm ⁻³	$10^3[\text{IO}_4^-]$ mol dm ⁻³	$10[\text{OH}^-]$ mol dm ⁻³	$10^6(\text{Inl. Rate})$ mol dm ⁻³ s ⁻¹	$10^5 k_{\text{obs}} (\text{s}^{-1})$	
				Expt.	Calcd.**
2.0	4.0	2.0	3.98	3.37	3.37
4.0	4.0	2.0	5.25	6.47	6.52
6.0	4.0	2.0	6.31	9.50	9.47
10.0	4.0	2.0	7.59	15.0	14.9
15.0	4.0	2.0	9.12	21.0	20.7
20.0	4.0	2.0	10.0	26.3	25.9
4.0	1.0	2.0	1.44	6.40	6.52
4.0	2.0	2.0	2.91	6.47	6.52
4.0	3.0	2.0	5.25	6.42	6.52
4.0	4.0	2.0	6.31	6.47	6.52
5.0	6.0	2.0	10.3	6.46	6.52
4.0	10.0	2.0	14.4	6.47	6.52
4.0	4.0	0.5	2.63	2.38	2.42
4.0	4.0	1.0	3.63	4.12	4.16
4.0	4.0	1.5	4.57	5.40	5.50
4.0	4.0	2.0	5.25	6.47	6.52
4.0	4.0	3.0	6.31	8.10	8.00
4.0	4.0	5.0	7.94	10.0	9.90

*Error $\pm 4\%$.

**Calculation based on rate law (10) and $K_1 = 3.26 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$, $K_2 = 4.42 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ and $k_1 = 1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$.

ferent experimental conditions were calculated and which are in good agreement with the experimental rate constants (Table 1).

The negligibly small effects of ionic strength and dielectric constant on the reaction rates are presumably due to the fact that the reaction is between a neutral and a charged species which is evident from the mechanism (Scheme 1). The sizeable negative entropy of activation is in agreement with the formation of the activated complex involved in the reaction.

It is interesting to note that periodate (existing as periodic acid in acid medium) being one of the strongest oxidising agents in acid medium, the oxidation of allyl alcohol in acid medium does not take place even in presence of different catalysts. But in alkaline medium, the reaction takes place with measurable velocity, thus receiving the attention to study the activity of periodate in such media.

Experimental

All the reagents used were of A.R. grade. Double-distilled water was used throughout. Stock solution of periodate was prepared by dissolving potassium metaperiodate (Riedel) and used after keeping for 24 h, and its concentration was verified iodometrically⁴. Allyl alcohol was purified¹⁰ and the distillate in the b.p. range 94–97° was used. The stock solution of allyl alcohol was standardised⁵. Sodium thiosulphate (Fischer) solution was prepared in water and standardised¹¹. Sodium perchlorate was used to maintain a constant ionic strength and NaOH (AnalaR) used to get the required alkalinity. Potassium iodate (Rechem) solution was prepared in water.

Kinetic runs : All kinetic runs were carried out under pseudo-first order conditions at $25.0 \pm 0.1^\circ$ unless stated otherwise. The reaction was initiated by mixing previously thermostated solutions of periodate and allyl alcohol which contained the required amounts of NaOH and NaClO₄. The progress of the reaction was followed by determining the concentration of unreacted periodate⁴.

At room temperature and in alkaline medium allyl alcohol was not hydrolysed to any significant extent. The effect of dissolved oxygen on the rate of the reaction was tested by preparing the reaction mixture and following the reaction in an atmosphere of nitrogen. No significant difference between the results, in presence and absence of air was obtained.

In view of the ubiquitous contamination of carbonate in basic solutions the effect of carbonate on the reaction was studied. The carbonate upto 1.0×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³ showed no effect on the reaction rate.

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